

Impact of a reclassification of Web of Science articles on bibliometric indicators

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Abstract

This work aims at evaluating a reclassification of Web of Science articles implemented at OST. Articles from the 254 scientific categories of the Web of Science were reclassified at article level in 242 modified categories and 11 disciplines using the method of S. Milojević (2020). The reclassification is based on paper references categories and it no longer assigns papers to multiple or to multidisciplinary categories. It improves the accuracy and the modularity of the WoS classification. As there are important changes in document assignment at the lowest level, usual indicators such as disciplinary profiles or field normalized indicators are significantly modified. This study examines some of these modifications to provide explanations for the recipients of OST reports. Changes in specialization indexes reveal specific journal choices by scientists. In a sample of 25 countries, Brazil and China offer examples of facilities or constraints for selecting WoS journals to publish certain research works.

Keywords: *WoS scientific categories, journal-based classification, paper-based classification, disciplinary specialization, MNCS indicator, publication strategy*

Introduction

Scientific classifications are necessary for bibliometric analyses and many classification schemes have been proposed and used. Historically, scientific publications were classified through journals. The classifications of WoS and Scopus databases have been challenged (Wang & Waltman, 2016) and new journal classifications have been proposed, using quantitative methods such as similarity measures of citation data or hybrid methods (Borner *et al.* 2012, Leydesdorff *et al.* 2017, Archambault *et al.* 2011). Multidisciplinary journals and journals with a lower specialization that does not fit with a precise classification scheme are hard to classify, however. These journals are usually assigned to several categories or to multidisciplinary categories. The use of multiple assignments leads to computational complications due to fractional disciplinary counts in indicator definitions. In addition, designing and implementing precise statistical methods that rely on sample simulations, like those developed by Thelwall and Fairclough (2017), is becoming more challenging.

Classifications at the level of individual publications avoid these disadvantages (Boyack *et al.* 2011; Klavans and Boyack 2017; Waltman and van Eck, 2012). High quality algorithms have been developed (Traag *et al.*, 2019). The CWTS classification for instance is based on direct citation data and open algorithms (Waltman & van Eck, 2012) and is now based on data of the OpenAlex database (Waltman & van Eck, 2024).

The French Science and Technology Observatory (OST) uses the WoS scientific categories as the basic level of its scientific nomenclature. To shift to a paper-based classification and to keep the frame of this scientific taxonomy, we implemented the reclassification algorithm of papers proposed by Milojević (2020), which assigns a single WoS category to each publication and reclassifies publications of multidisciplinary journals into disciplinary categories. The consistency between the category of a paper and of its references is enhanced by this reclassification. But changes of category assignment are numerous and this leads to significant changes in the usual bibliometric indicators. Shu *et al.* (2020) exhibit how their paper-level reclassification affects the productivity rankings of actors within disciplines.

As OST produces regular reports for French institutions, these modifications require a thorough understanding of the changes in standard bibliometric indicators that result from this reclassification. The paper aims to examine the changes in two indicators, the specialization index and the Mean Normalized Citation Score (MNCS). We examine the case of the 25 most productive countries on the period 2010-2022.

Section 1 describes the OST adaptation of Milojević's reclassification algorithm and how it is extended to a higher hierarchical level. In Section 2, modified categories are surveyed to identify dispersed and attractive categories with similar statistics to Shu *et al.* (2020). Section 3 shows how the distribution of world publications into disciplines is modified and how countries specialization indexes are related to migration rates between disciplines. Section 4 briefly examines the changes in countries MNCS, using the example of MNCS in Mathematics.

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1 Reclassification of WoS documents

Stasa Milojević (20120) suggested to keep nominal WoS categories and to revise the assignment of each article in these categories. Milojević’s reclassification is based on citation information, selecting their most frequent WoS category of the references of a paper as its paper-category (*P-category*). A unique category is chosen for each article. Papers in multidisciplinary journals are assigned to disciplinary categories.

1.1 Data

We use the whole in-house version of the WOS database³ as uploaded on May 5th, 2023. For the classification algorithm, we use all documents having WoS categories (called J-categories, as they are defined by the journal). Whereas all possible document in the database is used in the classification algorithm, we provide statistics only for the “standard perimeter” of documents that are of type Article, Review or Conference Proceedings (denoted *Corpus Y*).

1.2 Reclassification algorithm

Each paper in the database with at least 2 references in the base will be assigned a unique P-category (category assigned by paper) obtained by a reclassification algorithm very similar to Milojević’s (20120). The P-categories have the same titles as the original WoS J-categories. Ten multidisciplinary categories are removed, as there are not selected as possible P-categories⁴.

The algorithm selects a unique category for each paper which is the most frequent category of its references. WoS categories of references are counted with fractional counts and references in the 10 multidisciplinary categories are ignored. A first run allows to assign a P-category to the documents that have a unique maximal J-category. Two others runs are necessary to adjust the P-category of a paper to the P-categories of its references when they are modified. This closes the first step (Run 1, 2 and 3, Table 1). As Milojević (2020), we solve the last tied issues in a second step, adding the paper category to the category count (Run 4, Table 1) and, when ties remain, selecting the largest WoS category (Run 5, Table 1).

Table 1. Counts of reclassified documents at the different steps of the reclassification algorithm in corpus Z the subset of documents with at least 2 references. Counts are for Article, Review and Conference Proceedings document types

	Documents to classify	Documents with assigned P-category	Documents without assigned P-category	Non-assigned documents with tied references	Non assigned documents with multiD references
<i>Step1</i>					
Run 1	36,908,770	33,848,535	3,060,235	3,012,765	47,470
Run 2	36,908,770	34,482,274	2,426,496	2,406,552	19,944
Run 3	36,908,770	34,676,784	<u>2,231,986</u>	2,214,203	17,783
<i>Step 2</i>					
Run 4	<u>2,231,986</u>	997,342	1,234,644	1,224,853	9,791
Run 5	1,234,644	1,224,853	9,791	0	9,791
<i>Steps 1 + 2</i>	36,908,770	36,898,979	9,791		

A rule is finally defined to choose the P-category of 9,791 papers in multidisciplinary J-categories that have all their references in multidisciplinary J-categories. We assign these documents to the largest P-category of all reclassified papers from the same J-multidisciplinary category.

1.3 Aggregating categories into disciplines

OST uses a higher level of classification, that consists in 11 disciplines⁵ defined as sets of WoS categories - with some categories assigned to two disciplines (Bassecoulard & Zitt, 1999). To revise this level of the classification, we first define a P-discipline for each document with the previous algorithm initialized with the discipline assignment of documents derived from their journal. This step assigns a temporary P-discipline to each document. We then assign a single discipline for each P-category which is the largest P-discipline of the documents of the category. In some cases the category is broken down into two or more disciplines. The rule is to break down a category when the three following conditions are satisfied

- the predominant discipline is less than 80% on the category,

3 including 5 WoS Indexes: Science Citation Index expanded, Social Sciences Citation, Art & Humanities Citation, Essential Sources Citation Index, Conference Proceedings. The WoS-OST database contains scientific publications since 1999.

- the share of another discipline is more than 15% and has at least 5,000 documents,
- the selected disciplines are from different *domains*⁶.

For example, the category SUBSTANCE ABUSE (GM) is broken down into two categories SUBSTANCE ABUSE-Medical Research and SUBSTANCE ABUSE-Social Sciences with codes GM-02 and GM-SS (Table 2).

In these cases, documents of the category are assigned to the sub-category related to their P-discipline if it exists or to the sub-category of a discipline of the same large domain.

Table 2. The 11 P-categories broken down into 2 or 3 mono-discipline categories

CODE	CATEGORY	Disc 1	Disc 2	Disc 3
GM	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	02	SS	-
IG	ENGINEERING, BIOMEDICAL	07	02	-
LJ	GERONTOLOGY	SS	02	-
NE	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATI	02	SS	-
PI	MARINE & FRESHWATER BIOLOGY	06	03	-
PW	MEDICAL LABORATORY TECHNOLOGY	02	07	-
RZ	NURSING	02	SS	-
VE	PSYCHIATRY	02	SS	-
VX	PSYCHOLOGY, EXPERIMENTAL	SS	01	-
WC	REHABILITATION	02	SS	-
HB	EDUCATION, SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES	02	05	SS

We therefore have two classifications of documents into the 11 disciplines: the old OST disciplines derived from WoS categories and from the old correspondence: to be short, we call them *WoS disciplines* and we now call *OST disciplines* the new disciplines based on OST categories and on the new hierarchical correspondence just described (DataSet1, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>).

1.4 Final adjustments

Documents with less than two references

In the OST version of the WoS database (May 2023), there are 6,206,034 documents of type Article, Review and Conference Proceeding with less than two references in the base (corpus denoted W). We leave these documents in their J-Category (MULTIDISCIPLINARY categories excluded) - or the largest category if the journal is assigned to multiple categories. The size of the whole corpus Y of documents of type Article, Review and Conference Proceeding (called OST standard perimeter) is

$$\#Y = \#Z + \#W = 36,908,770 + 6,206,034 = 43,114,804$$

Removing 14 very small categories

Some P-categories have very few documents. This is the case for some recently introduced categories or for categories of interface fields that are mainly reclassified in one of the historic fields they emerged from. Too small categories may lead to hazardous normalization of individual scores. Therefore these small categories are removed and their documents are assigned to the second most frequent P-category of the whole set of their references (Table 3).

4 AGRICULTURE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (AH) - HUMANITIES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (BQ), BIOLOGY (CU), CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (DY) - ENGINEERING, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (IF), GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (LE), MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (PM), MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES (RO), PHYSICS, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (UI), PSYCHOLOGY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY (VJ).

5 Humanities (SH), Social Sciences (SS), Biology (01), Medical research (02), Applied Biology & Ecology (03),

Table 3. The 14 small categories merged with another category

REMOVED CATEGORY	# in Y (1999-2022)	MERGED CATEGORY	DISCIPLINES
RX NEUROIMAGING	44	RT CLINICAL NEUROLOGY	02
BV PSYCHOLOGY, BIOLOGICAL	302	CN BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES	01
QS QUANTUM SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	449	UH PHYSICS, ATOMIC, MOLECULAR & C	05
CT CELL & TISSUE ENGINEERING	453	IG02 ENGINEERING, BIOMEDICAL_02	01 – 02
OO MEDICAL ETHICS	505	PY MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	02
ML PRIMARY HEALTH CARE	1,284	PY MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	02
FS DANCE	1,358	YG THEATER	SH
MR HISTORY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES	1,408	MM HISTORY	SH
QL LOGIC	1,596	PQ MATHEMATICS	075 – 08
OU LIMNOLOGY	1,629	JA ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	06
AZ ANDROLOGY	1,803	WF REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY	02 – 01
VV SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	2,561	PY MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	SS – 02
PS SOCIAL SCIENCES, MATHEMATICAL	2,726	XY STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	SS – 08
VS PSYCHOLOGY, MATHEMATICAL	2,913	XY STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	SH – 08
Total	19,031		

1.5 OST classification: summary

The final 2-level OST new classification is therefore strictly hierarchical with a lower level of 242 P-categories (i.e. 254 WoS categories - 10 MULTIDISCIPLINARY + 12 split categories - 14 removed small categories) and a higher level of 11 disciplines.

After merging the 14 small categories in larger categories, the number of papers that stay in the same nominal category (i.e. with a P-category identical to one of its J-categories) is 54.03% for the corpus Y of all papers in the standard OST perimeter⁷ for the period 2010-2022 and 67.41% from the same corpus are reclassified in the same discipline. For these counts, we do not use fractional counts in WoS categories and we consider that a paper reclassified in one of its WoS category does not count as a category change.

This proportion may seem low and suggests that the reclassification process is susceptible to impact usual bibliometric indicators. However, this proportion of changes is similar to that of Chinese authors when they choose the category of their papers, independently from the category of the journal (Shu *et al.*, 2019). For Milojević (2020), 58% of documents with a unique non multidisciplinary WoS category are reclassified in the same category.

We show later that there are significant differences in these proportions between the categories.

Chemistry (04), Physics (05), Earth & Universe sciences (06), Engineering (07), Computer science (75), Mathematics (08)

6 Life sciences, Physics and Engineering, Humanities and Social Sciences

7 For this count, we do not use fractional counts in WoS categories and we consider that a paper reclassified in one of

Figure 1. Diagram of the reclassification process.

1.6 Consistency of the new classification

The reclassification of WoS articles is expected to improve the quality of the WoS journal classification. To measure the overall gain of consistency, we use two indicators: modularity and accuracy.

Modularity

The *modularity* of a classification is the objective function in the Leiden algorithm to detect connected communities in graphs (Traag *et al.*, 2019).

The global modularity H of a classification compares, in each class C , the proportion of observed edges to the expected proportion of edges in the random distribution, conditionally to the nodes degrees in the class. Edges between papers are direct citation links.

The formula for this modularity index is
$$H = \sum_C \frac{1}{2m} \left(e_C - \frac{K_C^2}{2m} \right)$$
 where e_C is the number of observed internal edges, K_C is the sum of the degrees of the nodes in the class and m is the number of undirected edges in the whole graph.

We compute the modularity of the new classification on corpus Y (documents of type Article, Review and Conference Proceeding) in the period 2010-2022, excluding documents from the removed multidisciplinary categories.

The comparison between WoS classification and OST reclassification shows a highly significant improvement in modularity. The modularity of the OST classification is much closer to that of meso-level topics of the Leiden Citation

Topics⁸ (Table 4).

Table 4. Modularity for three taxonomies (Corpus Y, period 2010-2022, full counts for links between WoS categories)

	# Categories	# Links	H	H sdt error	Confidence Interval 99%	
OST	242	398,776,924	0.30	0.04	0.20	0.40
WoS	244	1,217,037,695	0.08	0.01	0.06	0.10
Leiden meso topics	326	270,406,570	0.33	0.02	0.28	0.38

The OST modularity index was expected to be higher for OST classification compared to the WoS modularity due to its enhanced consistency between documents and their references. Furthermore, the OST modularity index is very similar to the modularity index of Leiden meso-topics. This result is very satisfactory since the Leiden classification maximizes this criterion for the definition of micro-topics.

Accuracy

Another simple index is used by Klavans and Boyack (2017) to compare the accuracies of various scientific taxonomies. Klavans and Boyack compare a classification of the scientific literature with reference sets of articles with very extensive bibliographies. They argue that such articles - usually review papers - frequently provide a summary of a research topic. The sets of their references can be "considered as expert-based partitions of the literature".

The concentration of these sets in a given taxonomy is thus proposed as an indicator of the taxonomy accuracy. They use the Herfindahl index of the references of a paper s

$$HE(s) = \sum_i p_i(s)^2 \text{ where } p_i(s) \text{ is the proportion of references of paper } s \text{ in class } i.$$

The accuracy of a classification is then measured by the mean of the concentrations of a set of *gold standard* papers

$$HE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_s HE(s).$$

Following Klavans & Boyack (2017), gold standard papers are selected as papers with at least 100 references in the database.

Computing the mean Herfindahl indexes of the references of 129,019 gold standard papers - ignoring the references in removed WoS categories for the WoS index - shows that the accuracy of the OST reclassification is significantly higher than the WoS accuracy and that it is very similar to that of the Leiden classification into meso level topics (Table 5).

Table 5. Concentration of Golden Standard papers for three classifications (Corpus Z, period 2010-2022)

Classification	# Categories	# Gold St	HE	HE(s) sdt error	HE Sdt error	Confidence Interval 99%	
OST	242	129,019	0.473	0.225	0.001	0.472	0.475
WoS	244	129,019	0.204	0.133	0.000	0.203	0.205
Leiden meso topics	326	129,019	0.458	0.247	0.001	0.457	0.460

The OST classification exhibits a highly significant improvement from the WoS with this second index. Again, the OST index is similar to the Leiden meso-level index⁹.

2 Exploring migrations from WoS to OST categories

As the overall rate of the OST classification revision is about 50%, It is instructive to look at how the categories are being

⁸ Data for *Leiden citation topics* as reported in the WoS database

⁹ Though a larger number of classes tends to decrease the concentration, the difference in class numbers between Leiden and OST classification does not have a significant impact on the difference between the two indexes. A linear transformation of the Leiden index in order to have the same variation range as the OST index would not change this

modified. When a paper from a WoS category C_1 is reclassified in a different OST category C_2 , we say that the paper *migrates* from C_1 to C_2 .

The statistics we provide are for corpus Y for the period of 2010-2022.

2.1 Migrations between categories

Attention could be focused on two types of categories: attracting categories that gather many papers from other J-categories and dispersed categories when many papers are reclassified in other P-categories. We use the following ratios similar to those of Shu *et al.* (2020).

Ratio J is the percentage of papers of a J-category that are classified in a different P-Category where we use fractional counts for documents in multiple WoS categories.

Ratio P is the percentage of papers of the P-category that come from a different J-category where we only count papers that have not the OST category as one of its WoS category.

When Ratio J is high, the J-category is dispersed among other P-categories. When Ratio P is high, the P-category attracts documents from other J-categories. A category is deeply modified if both ratios are high: 47% of the categories are in the upper right quadrant on Figure 1.

Figure 2. Comparison between journal classification and paper classification, by categories (2010-2022).

index before the third decimal.

BIOPHYSICS (DA), MATHEMATICAL & COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY (MC), MATERIALS SCIENCE, BIOMATERIALS (QE), PSYCHOLOGY (VI), NANOSCIENCE & NANOTECHNOLOGY (NS), MATHEMATICS, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS (PO), BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES (CN) are among the deeply modified categories.

In medical research, there is a rather loose relationship between the WoS medical specialities of journals and those of the papers published in those journals. Figure 1a shows that most OST categories have more than 50% of papers coming from another WoS category. The category MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL is a extreme case as 93.3% of papers in the OST category come from another WoS category, almost all of them in Medical Research (Table A1 in Appendix A).

Figure 2a. Comparison between journal classification and paper classification for Medical categories (2010-2022). Bubble size is proportional to the number of documents in the OST category.

Many categories in the Humanities discipline are conserved, partly because the documents with less than two references in the WoS base remain in their J-category (Fig. 1b). The perimeters of Psychology categories have been extensively modified, which is related to their connections with Life sciences.

Figure 2b. Comparison between journal classification and paper classification for categories of the Humanities discipline (2010-2022). Bubble size is proportional to the number of documents in the OST category.

An alluvial graph showing migrations between all categories would be useful to describe these category reorganizations more accurately. As such a large graph is difficult to analyse, we limit the description to migrations between disciplines.

2.2 Distribution of world publications into disciplines

Migrations between categories affect disciplines when they happen between categories that belong to different disciplines. The overall distribution across disciplines shows that discipline sizes are roughly preserved (Figure 2). The main changes concern Medical Research and Biology which have increased by +16.2% and +28.1% respectively. The size of other disciplines has been reduced (Applied Biology, -11.9%, Engineering -9.4% and Computer Science -16.4%).

Figure 3. World distribution of papers across disciplines according to WoS and OST classifications for the publication period 2010-2022.

The alluvial graph of migrations (Figure 3) shows many exchanges between the three disciplines in the Life science domain and also between Chemistry and Physics. The Engineering discipline is partly redistributed in Chemistry, Physics and Computer Science disciplines. This can be explained as research papers in Engineering journals using knowledge or skills from chemistry, physics or computer science.

Figure 4. Alluvial graph of migrations from disciplines based on J-categories - denoted *WoS Disciplines* - to disciplines based on P-categories - denoted *OST Disciplines* - for the whole world (Corpus Y, period 2010-2022, DataSet 2, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>).

Many papers that are originally published in Social Sciences journals are then reclassified as Medical Research. The division of certain categories between Social Sciences and Medical Research disciplines by OST (as indicated by the

bold categories in Table 6) contributes to this shift.

Table 6. Migration counts from WoS Social Sciences categories to OST Medical Research discipline (DataSet 5, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>)

WoS Category	Code	% in (Soc Sc → Med) migrations
PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	NE	31.50
PSYCHIATRY	VE	12.30
NURSING	RZ	10.55
HEALTH POLICY & SERVICES	LQ	8.33
REHABILITATION	WC	6.28
PSYCHOLOGY, CLINICAL	EQ	4.33
GERONTOLOGY	LJ	3.34
EDUCATION & EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH	HA	3.31
SUBSTANCE ABUSE	GM	2.37
SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	WV	2.34
SOCIAL SCIENCES, INTERDISCIPLINARY	WU	2.32
HOSPITALITY, LEISURE, SPORT & TOURISM	MW	1.44
SOCIAL WORK	WY	1.15
ECONOMICS	GY	1.07
		90.64

3 Impact of the reclassification on country specialization indexes

The specialization index of a country is the ratio of the share of papers in that country in the discipline to the same share in the whole world. When classification is revised, specialization indexes are modified because documents migrate from WoS to OST disciplines at different rates depending on the country. We report the ratio between the two specialization indexes (Fig. 4).

Countries with highest or lowest ratios mainly include Eastern countries. For example, some ratios have increased by more than 20% in China, Korea, Russia, Taiwan, and Pakistan. Some other ratios have decreased by more than 20% in Japan, Korea, Taiwan and Pakistan (Fig. 4). Conversely, changes for European countries and Australia are less than 10%. This means that these countries more often publish papers in journals of the “right” discipline, that is in a journal consistent with their references. This observation indicates that journal scopes may be more aligned with western publishing choices

Figure 5. Ratio of specialization indexes for the 25 countries with more than 150,000 publications (2010-2022). Country order is of decreasing total number of publications (DataSet3, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>).

To explore some of these variations, we use an approximation of the ratio ρ of the specialization indexes as a function of the number of documents of three sets :

- the set $WoS(Disc)$ of documents in the WoS discipline $Disc$,
- the set $NewOST(Disc)$ of documents in the OST Discipline $Disc$ that come from other WoS disciplines,
- the set $OldWoS(Disc)$ of documents that were in the WoS discipline $Disc$ and are reclassified in other OST disciplines.

This approximation (see Appendix B) is

$$\rho = 1 + [A(Disc, Country) - A(Disc, World)] - [B(Disc, Country) - B(Disc, World)] + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where

$$A(Disc, Country) = \frac{\# NewOST(Disc, Country)}{\# WoS(Disc, Country)} \quad \text{and}$$

$$B(Disc, Country) = \frac{\# OldWoS(Disc, Country)}{\# WoS(Disc, Country)} .$$

This means that the ratio depends on the difference of two rates between the country and the whole world: the attraction rate of (new) documents in the OST discipline and the loss rate of (old) documents from the WoS discipline.

Formula (1) explains the specialization ratio values represented in Figure 4 and provides additional information. It indicates whether a high or low value of the ratio is due to documents entering the OST discipline (Component A) or/and to documents exiting the WoS discipline (component B).

We show how to use this information in two examples.

3.1 Example 1: Country specialization in Applied Biology-Ecology

The low specialization ratios for Japan, Korea and Taiwan displayed in Figure 4 are mainly due to the high rate of papers leaving the WoS Applied Biology discipline, recorded in the B component (Table 7).

Table 7. Specialization ratio for Applied Biology (03) in four selected countries

Country	# NewOST(03)	# OldWoS(03)	# WoS(03)	# NewOST/ #WoS = A	# OldWoS/ #WoS = B	A(Country) - A(World)	B(Country)- B(World)	A-B+1 = Ratio + o
JAPAN	14,245.7	36,361.54	73,483.88	0.19	0.49	-0.08	0.11	0.81
KOREA	10,476.0	24,248.79	46,867.38	0.22	0.52	-0.05	0.13	0.82
TAIWAN	4,101.7	8,475.84	14,467.26	0.28	0.59	0.01	0.20	0.81
BRAZIL	27,728.6	34,755.65	134,909.64	0.21	0.26	-0.07	-0.13	1.06
WORLD	574,714.9	812,085.38	2,121,009.45	0.27	0.38	0.00	0.00	1.00

For these three countries, papers published in Applied Biology journals are more often (than the whole world) reclassified as Biology or Medical research works (Figure 5). In contrast, Brazil has fewer papers published in WoS Applied Biology journals that are reclassified as Biology or Medical Research works by OST.

Figure 6. Percentages of papers that leave the WoS Applied Biology discipline for another OST discipline.

Considering new papers in the Applied Biology OST discipline (Figure 6), Brazil has lower migrations rates from Biology, Chemistry, Earth & Universe Sciences. This means that Brazilian papers in Applied Biology are less frequently published in journals of other disciplines. Conversely, this is not true for Korea, Taiwan and Japan.

Figure 7. Percentages of papers reclassified in OST Applied Biology coming from other WoS disciplines

The two components of the specialization ratio show that Brazilian scientists choose Applied Biology journals to publish Applied Biology works with a high recall (low A component) and a high precision (low B component). This is related to a large access to WoS Brazilian journals in the field (Table B1 in the Appendix B).

This may be related to Brazil's high specialization in Applied Biology (Fig. B1 & B3 in Appendix B) and to governmental support in scientific journals. Agricultural research is essential to the economy of Brazil and is one of the most productive areas of national science. EMBRAPA¹⁰, the Brazilian agricultural research institution supervised by the Department of Agriculture, Livestock and Food Supply (MAPA) is a main actor in the field. The mission of the institution is to support agricultural production and agribusiness development, in a tropical environment. EMBRAPA research also covers topics as small farms, biodiversity conservation, and societal issues with an investment depending on the political context (Ollivier *et al.* 2019).

¹⁰ Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária

The government provides financial aid to support high-quality journals in various disciplines. The publishers of these WoS indexed Brazilian journals are mainly local universities and scientific associations and most of these journals have no or low Article Processing Charges (Rodrigues *et al.* 2020). During the 2000-2010 decade, efforts have been made to improve the influence and quality of national journals in agricultural science, resulting in 34 Agricultural science journals being indexed in the WoS between 2007 and 2009 (Vargas *et al.* 2014). This is a reason why Brazilian scientists easily publish in WoS journals in the field.

3.2 Example 2: Country specialization in Social Sciences

Canada, Brazil and Iran have low specialization ratios in Social Sciences. The *OldWoS* component (labelled B) is predominant for Canada and Iran (Table 8). This mainly corresponds to papers in Medical research journals reclassified in Social Sciences (Figure 7).

Table 8. Specialization ratio for Social Sciences in four selected countries

Country	# NewOST(SS)	# OldWoS(SS)	# WoS(SS)	# NewOST/ #WoS = A	# OldWoS/ #WoS = B	A(Country) - A(World)	B(Country)- B(World)	A-B+1 = Ratio + o
IRAN	7,068.0	13,124.9	24,641.9	0.29	0.53	0.05	0.22	0.83
CANADA	22,498.2	40,039.7	106,952.0	0.21	0.37	-0.02	0.06	0.92
BRAZIL	10,393.6	28,059.5	86,408.1	0.12	0.32	-0.11	0.01	0.88
CHINA	77,376.1	51,527.8	200,841.5	0.39	0.26	0.15	-0.06	1.21
WORLD	664,703.2	894,063.6	2,866,640.4	0.23	0.31	0.00	0.00	1.00

Figure 8. Percentages of papers leaving WoS Social Sciences for another OST discipline.

On the contrary, Brazil low ratio of specialization indexes is explained by a low value of the *New OST* Social Sciences component. There are less Social Sciences papers published in Humanities, Earth & Universe Sciences, Engineering or Computer sciences WoS journals (Figure 8).

Figure 9. Percentages of OST Social Sciences papers published in journals of other WoS disciplines for Brazil and China.

As for Applied Biology, this is related to the large access of Brazilian researchers to Brazilian journals. Among the Social Sciences papers of Brazilian authors in the 100 most used journals (2010-2022), there are 89% in Brazilian journals and still 58% for the papers in all WoS journals (Table B2 in Appendix). This indicates that either their research is aligned with global social science debates or it effectively integrates national research priorities with international research issues.

The case of China which shows a high increase of the specialization ratio in Social Sciences is related with many Social Sciences papers published in journals of other disciplines as Earth & Universe sciences, Engineering, Computer science and Mathematics (Fig. 8). These papers are mainly works in ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT, SOCIAL SCIENCES INTERDISCIPLINARY and BUSINESS (Fig. 9) which, together with EDUCATION & EDUCATION RESEARCH, represent 78.6% of the total Chinese publications in WoS Social Sciences journals.

Figure 10. Distribution of China *new papers* in OST Social Sciences by categories (2010-2022). Categories are presented in a descending order according to the number of Chinese papers.

The question is “Why are they many papers in Social Sciences - mainly in Economics, Management and Business - published in Earth & Universe sciences, Engineering, Computer science and Mathematics WoS journals ”?

A first answer would be that, because evaluation and employment committees are overly reliant on WoS, researchers tend to push their work to some WoS indexed journals or to journals with higher impact factors even when such a field is not quite relevant.

Another hypothesis is that researchers have to navigate between academic requirements and political constraints. Their strategy of publication may be adapted to a constrained research context. China's strategic priorities in economics research are focussed on economic growth, innovation, the impact of economic policies on national development and the development of ‘the economic theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics’ (Zhang, 2023). The debate about the Chinese characteristics of methods and theories does not facilitate publication in international sociology or science policy journals (Merle, 2007; Breffell & Dreyfuss, 2018). According to the CNKI Overseas Platform (2026), about 500 articles on this particular topic have been published from 2010 to 2022, in Chinese academic journals mainly not referenced in the WoS. A strategy could be to publish some of these works in WoS journals focused on application rather than in journals focused on economic theory and methods. These hypotheses should be supported by more data. In future work, this case study could be used as an example to analyse publication strategies of research stakeholders in various political contexts.

3.3 Interpreting changes in specialization

In this brief investigation, we discovered two countries that have distinct publishing strategies: Brazil scientists, which consistently publish their works in Applied Biology and Social Sciences in journals in those disciplines. In contrast, China scientists publish many of their Social Sciences works in WoS journals of a different category or journals not indexed in the WoS. The different local realities in terms of incentives and the various research strategies influence these choices.

In general, countries that are not European nor North American or Australian have one or two disciplines where some

specialization indices differ by more than 10% between the two classifications. This reflects a greater gap between the disciplines of their articles and those of the journals where they are published. This effect could be a result of a difference in scientific themes and methods between the country researchers and the editorial committees of WoS journals.

These examples serve as a starting point and require more accurate data and analysis to be validated. The objective here was to demonstrate that variations in disciplinary specialization indicators reflect different choices of journals.

4 Impact of the reclassification on MNCS indicators

Normalizing citation counts by field and year of publication as in the Normalized Citation Score (NCS) and its scale independent version MNCS (Waltman *et al.* 2010) is fairer than using citation counts. The database and its classification into fields affects the value of the related field-normalized indicators (Scheidsteger *et al.* 2023; Thelwall & Jiang, 2024).

We briefly examine the case of MNCS based on WoS or OST categories, averaged by discipline for the 25 countries, calculated using year 2019 data. The overall MNCS (all disciplines) has only been slightly modified, whereas more significant changes have been observed in disciplines as Physics, Engineering, Social Sciences, Humanities (Fig. C1 in the Appendix C) and Mathematics (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. MNCS Mathematics for WoS and OST normalizations (articles only, publication year 2019).

4.1 Breaking down the MNCS difference into intra- and inter-discipline components

We briefly explore the case of Mathematics to examine some issues related to this indicator.

The sum of normalized citation scores of the documents in a discipline changes

- when documents that are in the discipline for both classifications have different normalizing factors so that a same number of citations results in different normalized scores in the two classifications. These score differences contribute to the *intra-discipline* component of the difference of MNCS indicators;
- when documents are coming from one of the two sets of documents *NewOST(Math)* and *OldWoS(Math)* that are in the discipline for one classification and not for the other. Their contributions depend on the number of documents in these sets and on the difference between the scores of the documents in the two sets. They define the *inter-discipline* component of the MNCS difference (Formulas in Appendix C). Figure 12 displays the Mathematics MNCS difference broken down by intra- and inter-discipline components for the 25 countries.

Figure 12. Difference of MNCS between WoS and OST for the Mathematics discipline and its decomposition into intra- and inter-discipline components (year 2019, articles only, DataSet 4, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>).

The intra-discipline MNCS variation is due to migrations between Mathematics categories with different mean number of citations. The main differences are between MATHEMATICS (PQ) and MATHEMATICS, APPLIED (PN) categories (Table 9).

Table 9. Mean number of citations (the normalizing denominator) in Mathematics categories for WoS and OST classifications

Code	Category	WOS	OST
PN	MATHEMATICS, APPLIED	6.81	8.49
PQ	MATHEMATICS	3.83	3.54
XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	6.85	7.09
PO	MATHEMATICS, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	8.90	

Therefore a high rate of migration from WoS-PN to OST-PQ contributes to a positive intra-discipline MNCS variation and a high rate from WoS-PQ to OST-PN contributes to a negative intra-discipline MNCS. In our sample, countries with the highest migration rates from WoS-PN to OST-PQ are Italy, Poland, Spain, Brazil and China which are among those with the highest intra_discipline component (Fig. 13). Countries with high rates from WoS-PQ to OST-PN are among the countries with the lowest intra-discipline component.

Figure 13. Main migrations between Mathematics WoS and OST discipline (articles only, year 2019).

In this example, these two migration rates explain well the value of the intra-discipline component of MNCS difference. In the general case, other migrations between Mathematics categories of highly cited papers could also significantly contribute to this difference.

The inter-discipline component is a balance between the contributions DA and DB of the two sets *NewOST(Math)* and *OldWoS(Math)* (Fig. C1 in the Appendix C). A positive inter-discipline component is associated with high scores of the *NewOST(Math)* set of papers. These documents come from different non Mathematics disciplines. Their scores depend on the OST category where they arrive but also on their citation numbers but not on the mean citation number of the category they come from. It is then necessary to identify the papers with the highest citation numbers in order to explain a large *NewOST(Math)* contribution. Similarly, individual high scores of documents in *OldWoS(Math)* have to be identified when a high DB component leads to a low value of the inter-discipline component. Such an analysis is therefore specific for each research performer.

4.2 Discussion on MNCS sensitivity

The MNCS indicator has been carefully designed to integrate into a single indicator publications from heterogeneous disciplines and ages. In the case of Mathematics, for example, it is appropriate to distinguish between pure mathematical papers that advance the discipline and those that utilize mathematics as an analytical tool for research in other disciplines. These two research activities have distinct communities of potential readers with varying sizes and citation practices. However, understanding why the MNCS varies when changing the classification is laborious and returning to the citation numbers of individual papers may be necessary.

The brief analysis above confirms that this indicator is sensitive to the choice of classification. It is therefore safer to use this indicator with the most relevant available classification. In OST standard reports, we assume that, since 2023, field normalized indicators have been based on these modified categories.

5 Conclusion

The OST reclassification of scientific publications in modified WoS categories meets our first requirements for a scientific nomenclature: a classification at paper level, with no overlapping of categories and no multidisciplinary categories. It also restores a better consistency between each paper and its references and improves the overall accuracy as compared to the references of gold standard papers. The new categories have the same names as the WoS categories and this is convenient for the regular recipients of OST reports. However, the familiarity with WoS category names may be misleading because some category perimeters have significantly changed. OST is currently updating the category descriptions by supplying sets of keywords to replace the previous descriptions of the WoS categories. Programming the reclassification is simple, requires minimal resources, and is easily updated annually. This is therefore a cheap method to approach the properties of direct, efficient classifications such as the Leiden classification (Waltman & van Eck, 2012, Traag *et al.* 2019). The method proposed by Milojević (2020) is therefore considered highly relevant and has been successfully adopted by OST.

Differences between journal and paper categories result in changes in country specialization indexes. Large discrepancies reveal unusual journal choices which are more common among non western countries. National scientists have either facilitated or constrained choices when selecting WoS journals. This is observed for Brazilian scientists who easily publish their works in Applied Biology or in Social Sciences journals. Chinese scientists use alternative publication strategies to publish all their works in economics and sociology.

MNCS is an elaborate indicator which is designed for large and diverse set of publications but is sensitive to the classification. Analysing particular changes of the indicator may be difficult as it does not depend only on migration rates between fields. This indicator is more reliable if fields are consistent with the referencing/citation usage of each research community.

This study aims to provide a preliminary outline of how to comprehend the effects of switching from a journal to a paper level classification on usual indicators. As OST produces regular reports for French universities and institutions, it is important to explain the major changes in these indicators. The examples proposed in this paper provide a method for analysing such institutions. This is necessary because indicators for highly specialized institutions can be significantly altered and, for those institutions, it may be useful to have specific interactions with OST to assist them in their self-assessment.

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Author contributions

Agénor Lahatte: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, software, validation, writing review

Élisabeth de Turckheim: conceptualization, formal analysis, validation, visualization, writing.

Competing interests

No competing interests to declare.

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Data availability

The data used in this paper is proprietary and cannot be posted in a repository. Intermediate data are given in Lahatte&Turckheim (2025).

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7 APPENDIX A . Migrations to the OST category MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL (PY)

Table A1. 30 first WoS categories migrating to the OST- MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL category

Code	WoS CATEGORY	% in OST-PY	Code	WoS CATEGORY	% in OST-PY
NE	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONA	10.87	IA	ENDOCRINOLOGY & METABOLISM	1.62
HL	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	7.30	PT	MEDICAL INFORMATICS	1.40
PY	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	6.68	LI	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	1.36
NN	INFECTIOUS DISEASES	4.81	WE	RESPIRATORY SYSTEM	1.32
TU	PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACY	3.95	FF	EMERGENCY MEDICINE	1.29
DQ	CARDIAC & CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEMS	3.92	SD	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY	1.28
LQ	HEALTH POLICY & SERVICES	2.94	DM	ONCOLOGY	1.16
RZ	NURSING	2.51	HB	EDUCATION, SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES	1.09
QA	MEDICINE, RESEARCH & EXPERIMENTAL	2.44	QU	MICROBIOLOGY	1.08
YA	SURGERY	2.32	VE	PSYCHIATRY	1.05
TQ	PEDIATRICS	2.11	DS	CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE	0.94
NI	IMMUNOLOGY	2.10	SA	NUTRITION & DIETETICS	0.93
ML	PRIMARY HEALTH CARE	1.99	ZA	UROLOGY & NEPHROLOGY	0.90
ZD	PERIPHERAL VASCULAR DISEASE	1.92	MA	HEMATOLOGY	0.88
RT	CLINICAL NEUROLOGY	1.64	BA	ANESTHESIOLOGY	0.85
		57.49			17.15

8 APPENDIX B. Specialization indexes

8.1 Country specialization by discipline

Figure B1. Brazil specialization in the 11 disciplines.

Figure B2. China specialization in the 11 disciplines.

Figure B3. Country specialization in Applied Biology.

Figure B4. Country specialization in Social Sciences.

8.2 Approximation of the ratio of specialization indexes ρ

The ratio of the specialization indexes between OST and WoS ρ is such that

$$\frac{\#OST(Disc, Country)}{\#WoS(Disc, Country)} = \rho \frac{\#OST(Disc, World)}{\#WoS(Disc, World)}$$

To relate this inequality with numbers of migrations, we define

$\#OST(Disc)$ as the total number of papers in the OST discipline $Disc$,

$\#NewOST(Disc)$ the number of papers in OST_Disc that come from another WoS discipline,

$\#OldWoS(Disc)$ the number of papers in WoS_Disc that leave to another OST discipline.

$$\text{As } \#OST(Disc) = \#WoS(Disc) + \#NewOST(Disc) - \#OldWoS(Disc)$$

$$\frac{\#OST(Disc)}{\#WoS(Disc)} = 1 + \frac{\#NewOST(Disc)}{\#WoS(Disc)} - \frac{\#OldWoS(Disc)}{\#WoS(Disc)}$$

$$\text{Using, } \frac{1+x}{1+y} = 1 + x - y + o(x+y) ,$$

a first order approximation of the specialization ratio is

$$\rho = 1 + A(Country) - A(World) - (B(Country) - B(World)) + \epsilon$$

where

$$A(Country) = \frac{\#NewOST(Disc, Country)}{\#WoS(Disc, Country)} \quad \text{and} \quad B(Country) = \frac{\#OldWoS(Disc, Country)}{\#WoS(Disc, Country)}$$

8.3 *Brazilian publications in Applied Biology*

Table B1. Number of Brazilian papers among the 40 most used journals by Brazilian scientists in Applied Biology (Period 2010-2022 data). *Brazilian journals are in grey cells.*

Journal	#Papers	%
ZOOTAXA	3513	7.01
SEMINA CIENCIAS AGRARIAS	3151	6.28
CIENCIA RURAL	3106	6.19
ARQUIVO BRASILEIRO DE MEDICINA VETERINARIA E ZO	2141	4.27
PESQUISA AGROPECUARIA BRASILEIRA	1755	3.50
BIOSCIENCE JOURNAL	1722	3.43
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ZOOTECNIA BRAZILIAN JOURN	1667	3.32
PESQUISA VETERINARIA BRASILEIRA	1649	3.29
PLOS ONE	1579	3.15
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENGENHARIA AGRICOLA E AME	1491	2.97
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FRUTICULTURA	1467	2.93
PHYTOTAXA	1427	2.85
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIENCIA DO SOLO	1327	2.65
REVISTA CAATINGA	1250	2.49
CIENCIA FLORESTAL	1219	2.43
ACTA SCIENTIAE VETERINARIAE	1164	2.32
FOOD SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	1142	2.28
REVISTA CIENCIA AGRONOMICA	1101	2.20
ANAIS DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE CIENCIAS	1048	2.09
BIOTA NEOTROPICA	1030	2.05
HORTICULTURA BRASILEIRA	1002	2.00
FOOD RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	998	1.99
REVISTA ARVORE	985	1.96
ACTA HORTICULTURAE	967	1.93
GENETICS AND MOLECULAR RESEARCH	916	1.83
LWT FOOD SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	916	1.83
ACTA BOTANICA BRASILICA	899	1.79
FOOD CHEMISTRY	879	1.75
PLANTA DANINHA	868	1.73
CIENCIA E AGROTECNOLOGIA	828	1.65
BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF BIOLOGY	778	1.55
SCIENTIA FORESTALIS	762	1.52
FLORESTA E AMBIENTE	756	1.51
ACTA SCIENTIARUM AGRONOMY	752	1.50
NEOTROPICAL ENTOMOLOGY	710	1.42
ENGENHARIA AGRICOLA	657	1.31
SCIENTIFIC REPORTS	657	1.31
SCIENTIA AGRICOLA	640	1.28
NEOTROPICAL ICHTHYOLOGY	616	1.23
BRAGANTIA	614	1.22
<i>Total in the 40 first journals</i>	50149	100.00
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (31 journals)</i>	38556	76.88
<i>Total in the 100 first journals</i>	74023	
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (86 journals)</i>	49079	66.30
<i>Total in all journals (3810 journals)</i>	148252	
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (327 journals)</i>	53755	36.26

8.4 Brazilian publications in Social Sciences

Table B2. Number of Brazilian papers among the 40 most used journals by Brazilian scientists in Social Sciences (Period 2010-2022 data). *Brazilian journals are in grey cells.*

Journal	#Papers	%
REVISTA IBERO AMERICANA DE ESTUDOS EM EDUCACAO	1287	6.18
EDUCAR EM REVISTA	828	3.97
REMEA REVISTA ELETRONICA DO MESTRADO EM EDUCACAO AMBIENTAL	817	3.92
EDUCACAO	703	3.37
MOVIMENTO	688	3.30
REVISTA PRAXIS EDUCACIONAL	663	3.18
QUAESTIO IURIS	651	3.12
DIREITO E PRAXIS	637	3.06
REVISTA ELETRONICA EM GESTAO EDUCACAO E TECNOLOGIA AMBIENTAL	584	2.80
REVISTA DE DIREITO DA CIDADE CITY LAW	580	2.78
CONFIN REVUE FRANCO BRESILIEENNE DE GEOGRAPHIE REVISTA FRANCO BRASILEIRA DE GEOGRAFIA	563	2.70
EM QUESTAO	554	2.66
REVISTA GEOGRAFICA DE AMERICA CENTRAL	553	2.65
ETD EDUCACAO TEMATICA DIGITAL	548	2.63
REVISTA ON LINE DE POLITICA E GESTAO EDUCACIONAL	535	2.57
CIENCIA & SAUDE COLETIVA	531	2.55
ECCOS REVISTA CIENTIFICA	516	2.48
CUSTOS E AGRONEGOCIO ON LINE	503	2.41
DIALOGIA	483	2.32
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MARKETING	466	2.24
INFORMACAO & SOCIEDADE ESTUDOS	452	2.17
COMUNICACOES	441	2.12
REVISTA TEMPOS E ESPACOS EDUCACAO	435	2.09
PERSPECTIVAS EM CIENCIA DA INFORMACAO	428	2.05
POLEMICA	424	2.03
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCACAO DO CAMPO BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF RURAL EDUCATION	420	2.02
REVISTA TECNOLOGIA E SOCIEDADE	418	2.01
GEO UERJ	415	1.99
ATELIE GEOGRAFICO	411	1.97
REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FUTSAL E FUTEBOL	400	1.92
ROSA DOS VENTOS TURISMO E HOSPITALIDADE	398	1.91
REVISTA ELETRONICA DE ESTRATEGIA E NEGOCIOS REEN	398	1.91
DESENVOLVIMENTO E MEIO AMBIENTE	397	1.91
NAVUS REVISTA DE GESTAO E TECNOLOGIA	394	1.89
REVISTA ACTA GEOGRAFICA	394	1.89
REVISTA DE GESTAO E SECRETARIADO GESEC	391	1.88
REVISTA ELETRONICA PESQUISEDUCA	389	1.87
REVISTA GESTAO & TECNOLOGIA JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND TECHNOLOGY	382	1.83
RAE REVISTA DE ADMINISTRACAO DE EMPRESAS	382	1.83
REVISTA AMBIENTE CONTABIL	377	1.81
<i>Total in the 40 first journals</i>	20836	100.00
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (38 journals)</i>	19720	94.64
<i>Total in the 100 first journals</i>	59168	
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (87 journals)</i>	53876	91.06
<i>Total in all journals (5675 journals)</i>	99873	
<i>Total and % in Brazilian journals (341 journals)</i>	65566	65.65

9 APPENDIX C. MNCS

9.1 Country MNCS for four disciplines

Figures C1. MNCS variation for 4 disciplines, 25 countries, year 2019 (DataSet 4, <https://zenodo.org/records/15606281>).

9.2 Breaking down MNCS differences into intra- and inter-discipline components

$NewOST(Math)$ is the set of documents in the OST discipline Mathematics from another WoS discipline, $OldWoS(Math)$ are the documents in the WoS discipline Mathematics reclassified in another OST discipline. In $Math^2$ are the documents common to $WoS(Math)$ and $OST(Math)$.

$$NCS_{OST}(OST(Math)) = NCS_{OST}(Math^2) + NCS_{OST}(NewOST(Math))$$

$$NCS_{WoS}(WoS(Math)) = NCS_{WoS}(Math^2) + NCS_{WoS}(OldWoS(Math))$$

$$D = MNCS_{OST}(OSTMath) - MNCS_{WoS}(WoSMath) = D1 + D2$$

$$D1 = \frac{NCS_{OST}(Math^2)}{\#OSTMath} - \frac{NCS_{WoS}(Math^2)}{\#WoSMath} \quad \text{Intra-discipline component}$$

$$D2 = DA - DB = \frac{NCS_{OST}(NewOST(Math))}{\#OSTMath} - \frac{NCS_{WoS}(OldWoS(Math))}{\#WoSMath} \quad \text{Inter-discipline component}$$

9.3 MNCS inter-discipline component

Decomposition of the Mathematics inter-discipline MNCS variation $D2$ into DA ($NewOST$ contribution) and DB ($OldWoS$ contribution)

Figure C2. Decomposition of the inter-discipline variation for the MNCS in Mathematics for 25 countries.

To further explore the case of a country, it is necessary to pick up highly cited documents in the *NewOST* set and to check that they are more cited than those in their OST category. For example, Table A1 displays the WoS disciplines of the main categories arriving in *NewOST(Math)* for the two countries with the highest inter-discipline component. Exploring these documents is a good way to start the search for influential documents, which have a higher number of citations than the world in their OST category. For instance when there is a high DA component, one could search papers with mathematics references arriving from other discipline journals that are numerous and more cited than standard mathematics papers.

Table C1. Distribution of *NewOST(Math)* into WoS disciplines for The Netherlands and Egypt (fractional counts by address)

Country	WoS Disc code	WoS Discipline	OST Cat code	OST category	# (WoS disc → OST Cat)	# <i>New Math</i>	% in <i>New Math</i>	% in <i>New Math</i>
NETHERLANDS	SS	SOCIAL SCIENCES	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	33.14	156.86	21.12	61.49
NETHERLANDS	075	COMPUTER SCIENCE	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	14.70		9.37	
NETHERLANDS	SH	HUMANITIES	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	14.19		9.05	
NETHERLANDS	01	BIOLOGY	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	12.03		7.67	
NETHERLANDS	02	MEDICAL RESEARCH	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	11.29		7.20	
NETHERLANDS	07	ENGINEERING	XY	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	11.10		7.08	
EGYPT	05	PHYSICS	PN	MATHEMATICS, APPLIED	34.63	90.86	38.11	72.31
EGYPT	07	ENGINEERING	PN	MATHEMATICS, APPLIED	21.85		24.04	
EGYPT	075	COMPUTER SCIENCE	PN	MATHEMATICS, APPLIED	9.22		10.15	